

April 2026

Newsletter – Upcoming activities 2026

To NFPs for Food- and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses and OCPs for Microbiology

Dear colleagues,

We are pleased to share the first EURL-PH-FWDB newsletter, bringing together key information on upcoming activities for the network laboratories in 2026.

Following the Information meeting held on 19 of March, this newsletter provides a consolidated overview and updates on planned EURL activities and events, with some additional context to support your planning and participation.

EURL contacts and a full activity calendar are provided in Annexes 1 and 2. In addition, all EURL activities are described in more detail in the [Annual work plan – Year 1](#).

Information from the EURL will typically be shared *via* the EURL-website and the FWDB Collaboration site; both are currently under development. The next newsletter is planned for the end of 2026.

Support to the network laboratories

Network laboratories may request EURL to provide:

- **Reference diagnostics and characterisation services**, as well as **reference materials** related to *Salmonella*, STEC, *Listeria*, *Campylobacter* and *Shigella*
- **Scientific advice and technical support** related to *Salmonella*, STEC, *Listeria*, *Campylobacter*, *Shigella*, *Vibrio spp.*, *Yersinia spp.* (excluding *Y. pestis*)

The lists of available reference diagnostics and characterisation services, and reference materials can be accessed using following links:

- [Reference diagnostics and characterisation services](#)
- [Reference strains for *Campylobacter*](#)
- [Reference strains for *Listeria*](#)
- [Reference strains for *Salmonella* and *Shigella*](#)

- [Reference strains for STEC and DEC](#)

Requests for support to the EURL-PH-FWDB will be collected through a dedicated online form. If you wish to request support from the EURL-PH-FWDB, including the provision of reference materials, diagnostics and characterization services, as well as scientific and technical advice, please complete the form available [here](#).

External Quality Assessments (EQAs)

This year, several EQAs will be organised to support harmonisation and quality assurance across the network, an overview of the 2026 EQAs is reported below:

Spring

- *Listeria monocytogenes* genotyping and cluster analysis.
Invitation was sent on 20.02.2026
- *Salmonella* serotyping and cluster analysis.
Invitation was sent on 26.02.2026

Autumn

- *Campylobacter* species, genotyping and cluster analysis
Invitation is planned to be sent in June 2026
- *Shigella* species, genotyping and cluster analysis
Invitation is planned to be sent in June 2026
- STEC virulence-gene detection, stx-subtyping, serotyping and cluster analysis
Invitation is planned to be sent in August 2026

Each country is invited to nominate one participating laboratory per EQA.

Training Activities

In-person trainings:

Training 1: *Salmonella* training focused on basic short-read data analysis, serotyping, and cluster analysis.

Date: 3–4 June (RIVM, the Netherlands)

Participation: 25 participants (NFPs, OCPs, and other nominated participants).

Training 2: Training on identification and characterisation of diarrhoeagenic *E. coli* (focus on STEC).

- **Session 1:** 7–11 September (ISS, Italy)
- **Session 2:** 14–18 September (ISS, Italy)

Both *E. coli* sessions are identical and will host 10 participants.

An invitation to nominate participants for both trainings was sent on 09.04.2026. The deadline for participant applications is 24.04.2026.

Scientific and technical webinars

An open webinar (topic to be confirmed) will be organised **in the autumn 2026** for the full network. Participation is unlimited.

Laboratory network Survey

We are planning to administer a network-wide survey to assess the following:

- Capacity and capability across laboratories
- Support and training needs

Important dates:

- **Mid-June:** Webinar to introduce the survey strategy and aims
- **Mid-June:** Invitation sent to NFPs and OCPs
- **Mid-September:** deadline for nationally coordinated response

Your input will help shaping future EURL activities and support the evaluation of EURL impact at both national and EU levels. The results of the survey will be summarised and shared with network laboratories, either during the Laboratory Network Meeting or in a dedicated webinar.

Laboratory Network meeting

Date: 8–9 October (SSI, Denmark)

This will be our first in-person meeting and will focus on technical and scientific topics across different pathogens.

Participation is limited to approximately 30 participants (NFPs and OCPs).

We encourage you to already mark these dates in your calendar. Further details, including information on how to register and agendas, will be shared in due course.

If you have any questions or would like to express interest in specific activities, please do not hesitate to contact us.

Kind regards,

EURL-PH-FWDB team

Annex 1 EURL mailboxes

General:

EURL-PH-FWDB@ssi.dk

Support for reference diagnostics and characterisation, reference strains, scientific and technical support:

EURLFWB@iss.it

EQAs:

EQA-Salmonella-EURL-PH-FWDB@rivm.nl

EQA-Shigella-EURL-PH-FWDB@rivm.nl

EQA-Cam-EURL-PH-FWDB@ssi.dk

EQA-Lis-EURL-PH-FWDB@ssi.dk

EQA-Ecoli-EURL-PH-FWDB@iss.it

Trainings:

Train-EURL-PH-FWDB@ssi.dk

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Annex 2 EURL activity and event calendar

Date	Activity	Topic	Participants	Organiser
Spring	EQA	<i>Salmonella</i> serotyping and cluster analysis	One laboratory per country	RIVM
Spring	EQA	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> genotyping and cluster analysis	One laboratory per country	SSI
3-4 June	In-person training (<i>Salmonella</i>)	On basic short-read data analysis, <i>Salmonella</i> serotyping and cluster analysis	25 participants (NFPs, OCPs, other nominated participants)	RIVM
June	Survey	Capacity and capability, support and training needs	Nationally coordinated response	SSI
7-11 September	In-person training (<i>E. coli</i> I)	Identification and characterization of diarrhoeagenic <i>E. coli</i> , with the focus on STEC	10 participants (NFPs, OCPs, other nominated participants)	ISS
14-18 September	In-person training (<i>E. coli</i> II)	Identification and characterization of diarrhoeagenic <i>E. coli</i> , with the focus on STEC	10 participants (NFPs, OCPs, other nominated participants)	ISS
8-9 October	Laboratory Network meeting	Technical and scientific topics across different pathogens	approx. 30 participants (restricted to NFPs and OCPs)	SSI
Autumn	Webinar	TBD	Unlimited	SSI
Autumn	EQA	<i>Campylobacter</i> species, genotyping, cluster analysis	One laboratory per country	SSI
Autumn	EQA	<i>Shigella</i> species, genotyping, cluster analysis	One laboratory per country	RIVM
Autumn	EQA	STEC virulence-gene detection, stx-subtyping, serotyping and cluster analysis	One laboratory per country	ISS